

REPRESENTATIONS OF SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE ENVIRONMENTS IN DATA MODELS AND DIGITAL PRESERVATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract – One of the ongoing challenges of digital preservation practice is how to document and preserve software and hardware requirements in a digital preservation system. This poster maps out the various scenarios for how the Art Gallery of New South Wales (The Gallery) have conceptualised representing software and hardware requirements for complex time-based artworks (TBA) in our digital preservation system, Preservica.

The Art Gallery of New South Wales (the Gallery) is currently completing the implementation of a digital preservation system, Preservica. As the Gallery contains a lot of time-based artworks (TBA) and variable media collected archives, capturing the environments that were used to create the works is essential their preservation. One of the key considerations for ongoing preservation actions and future access for these works is emulation. This requires determining how best to represent software and hardware requirements within Preservica. This poster illustrates 3 proposed scenarios for how The Gallery could do so, depending on common environments found within the collection and required metadata. This is not “out of the box” functionality and will require considerable testing before we decide on the best approaches.

The team is looking at three possible scenarios and will test how each works in the Preservica system. A one-to-one dedicated environment that is specific to that artwork alone, a one-to-many environment that

may be used for multiple artworks, and a model for capturing the relationships between environmental content objects and the associated emulation environments.

SCENARIO 1

The first option for representing software and hardware requirements as Environmental Objects (EO) within Preservica can be seen in Fig. 1, below. This scenario is to create more “generic” environmental objects that may be linked to multiple artworks. The EO is ingested as a Structural object that can be linked or related to different artworks. Noting that custom metadata fields will be needed to document any additional technical requirements or hardware dependencies.

Figure 1. This a data model represents an environmental object as a structural object that can be linked to multiple different collection items.

SCENARIO 2

The second scenario is a model for capturing the relationships between environmental content objects and the associated emulation environments. This is where multiple emulation environments have been identified to support multiple artworks. For example, there could be one emulation environment for Windows 95, another for Windows 2000 and another for Mac OS 9. Each emulation environment is packaged as separate Information Objects (IOs) within a single Structural Object (SO). As shown in Fig.2 below, each artwork that requires a particular emulation environment is linked to it via descriptive metadata.

Figure 2. Data Model for a dedicated environmental object for one Archival collection item.

SCENARIO 3

This scenario (Fig.3) is where there is a one-to-one relationship between a collection item and the EO. Given the complexities of the TBA collection, the different Operating Systems (OS), software and hardware that artists use, and the artists intention for how the artwork should be installed and be displayed, many of artworks will have dedicated environmental objects. The EO is ingested as an Information Object (IO) as part of the SIP package (Structural Object - SO) that contains all the different IOs, which are the

different representation types identified from The Gallery Data Model.

Figure 3. This is a data model for environments relating to a collection of artworks and the corresponding emulation environment. The related artworks are linked to the object.

The complex nature of the Gallery collections means that we need to document and capture environmental objects in our digital preservation system. This is especially important as The Gallery, and many other cultural institutions, are looking to emulation as an increasingly viable method for preservation and access.

The representation of environmental objects is not something that has been adopted by digital preservation systems quite yet. Without out-of-the-box functionality, The Gallery will test these scenarios to determine how best to represent supporting software and hardware as Environmental Entities for future emulation purposes.

Submission Type - Poster
Keywords - Workflows, Software, Emulation
Conference Topics - Haerenga - Journey

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